

Available online at www.behaviorsciences.com

Reef Resources Assessment and Management Technical Paper

ISSN: 1607-7393

RRAMT 2014- Vol. 40, 2014, 1

The examination of the affection's purposes in Qur'an and its impact on human evolutionary behaviour

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Abstract

The tribulations have always created a halo of ambiguity in human's mind and have made him to confront this question of why some people's lives are always difficult but some other's lives are happy and comfortable? Holy Qur'an in many verses, has considered the life and death creation, heaven and the earth and its ornaments for human testing to determine the most righteous people, and since tongue faith is not enough to determine human faith degree, the hardship and tribulations battlefield enlighten these degrees. Therefore, two main purposes are effective in human tribulations: differentiation and maturation. Affliction causes differentiation and separation of believers from the disbelievers and the hypocrites who were tempted by negligence and finally it leads to proper growth and their behavior's evolution. Affliction for believers is the forgiveness of sins and for divine prophets and imams and for pious people, leads to degrees promotion and earn great rewards. Catastrophe and blessings are two affliction tools, so that "patience" in catastrophe and "gratitude" in blessing time, are the signs of their glory. Every utterance is that the helot can go through the continuous process of submission way well. Just the way that starts from the thinking. This thinking makes him to mention God and makes him away from failing sleep and then makes his God witness eyes on the facts and gifts him divine cognition and knowledge and by this cognition, he can withstand patiently in the divine test and affliction storms and life hardships and since he has chosen this way with discernment seen and the eyes which are open to facts, he will be satisfied of divine mishap. These two moral virtues, are behavior evolution peak and a pretext for the suffering faithful, so that in hardship and difficulty times he doesn't feel double sorrow and in the time that the blessings are less he doesn't neglect and forget God, but he will be embossed with moral minds evolution by balancing his behavior. This is the same full-fledged human whose upbringing is the creation goal.

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Keywords: affliction, blessing, catastrophe, evolution, differentiation, behavior

1. Introduction

One of the human feature than other creatures, is his authority, human being is moving toward his main goal; namely final perfection with his authority. God's essence, putting people at events in social and personal life, will appear his

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power and hidden talents. The events that are tailored to his destination, and we gave it the name "test" and "testing", reveal his inner condition of the acceptance or rejection of the will of God. This divine tradition that is the same as affliction tradition, takes human beings as a general and always current tradition [1]. In this paper, we figure on examining the affliction aims and its effects on human behavior.

2. Affliction lexical meaning

Some of the linguists know the affliction as two basis: 1- from the roots of "afflict" which means obsolescence and deterioration 2- from the root of "trials" which means trial and examination.

Some other linguistics knows that as a principle of meaning. A group like Raghīb Isfahani, knows its essential meaning "afflict", namely obsolescence, and refers all these word uses to this meaning. The other group believes that its basis is "trial" and knows it as an experience and testing which is with transformation and changing.

Affliction's purposes

Some parts of disasters are from God and are necessary for the world's lifetime and are not only because of the wisdom and expediency, but also have some benefits. Though most of these disasters, are apparently intensity, but in fact are favors and blessings [4]. By using the infinite science of Qur'an and contemplation in its verses, the aims of these kinds of disasters can be divided in many major parts.

3. human differentiation

Human differentiation and separation from each other are the affliction goals which have following subsidiaries:

3.1. 1 True faith and false faith differentiation

The holy God put the people who declare their faith at risk, to determine their words and faith truth:

AL-ANKABOOT (THE SPIDER)(2-3): « وَ لَقَدْ فَتَنَّا الَّذِينَ مِنْ قَبْلِهِمْ فَلَيَعْلَمَنَّ اللَّهُ الَّذِينَ «صَدَقُوا وَ لَيَعْلَمَنَّ الْكَاذِبِينَ» (do men think that they will be left alone on saying, "we believe", and that they will not be tested? we did test those before them, and Allah will certainly know those who are true from those who are false.)

By examining the testing in the life and property, the results of these true and false revealed [5]. Because it is the examination that reveals humans conscience. This appearance necessity is to fix the people's faith whose faith is actual and to invalidate the people's faith whose faith is merely a claim [6]. The reward and happiness that is promised in turn for belief, is applied on true faith. the people faith is bound to blessing and to the limit that they don't loss, Qur'an doesn't count in their faith as a true faith, but they themselves claim for they believes.

AL-HAJJ (THE PILGRIMAGE) (11) « أَطْمَأَنَّ بِهِ وَ إِنْ أَصَابَتْهُ فِتْنَةٌ انْقَلَبَ عَلَى وَجْهِهِ وَ مِنَ النَّاسِ مَنْ يَعْْبُدُ اللَّهَ عَلَى حَرْفٍ فَإِنْ أَصَابَهُ خَيْرٌ «
« خَيْرَ الدُّنْيَا وَ الْآخِرَةِ

(there are among men some who serve Allah, as it were, on the verge: if good befalls them, they are, therewith, well content; but if a trial comes to them, they turn on their faces: they lose both this world and the hereafter: that is loss for all to see!)

3.1.2 The Benefactor and wicked differentiation

Qur'an knows the life and death means for evaluating the benefactor from the wicked.

AL-MULK (THE SOVEREIGNTY)(2) « الَّذِي خَلَقَ الْمَوْتَ وَ الْحَيَاةَ لِيَبْلُوَكُمْ أَيُّكُمْ أَحْسَنُ»

«عملاً» (he who created death and life, that he may try which of you is best in deed).

Thus, the disaster and examination are not only regarded as the main purpose of the creation, themselves, but also the main purpose is "which of you is best in deed" and the main purpose of the creation is the benefactors or the people who have acted better than the other people and they were honorable in exams. God examines human by giving him blessing or depriving him of the blessing, but the human doesn't take it to consideration as it is worthy. When he is favored, he imagine that's because of his competence, therefore he sinks in ignorance and vanity and then God takes

that and puts him in punishment from the opulence [7] which is referred as “Luring” tradition. The God’s management is not out of three modes against the sins of the servants.

1-the servant notice his sins and return back to God so that he is “repentant” and Allah accepts his penitence. 2- the servant insists on his sins and also the God puts him in disaster to wake him up so that the God has provided his “caution” appliance. 3- the person sinks in rebellion and sin so that is not deserved of non of the above two cases, the result is that the God gifts him blessing instead of disaster and based on “expectancy” tradition or divine deadline, doesn’t punish him immediately; because the God action is not along with precipitance. Finally, with all these blessings, leads to his punishing and awakening so that whether the divine guidance plan has been acted, or the rebels continue to their outburst and god will leave them. The major difference between affliction and luring means that in the affliction, not only the grace and attention to human is not taken away by god, but also God takes the person in his own evolution way by means of “ mention”, it’s against luring that because of frequent rebellions, divine success is withdrawn and the human will be subsided and his only help is God deadline and not being hasty in the punishment, but most of the rebellious do not prize this opportunity. Paying attention to the luring meaning, indicates that in such a case, the servant forgets thanksgiving blessings and also retraction of sins.

It should not be assumed that a faithful person will be in comfort and after believing the world hardships and difficulties are not for him[8]. One of the most pivotal verses that indicates the purpose of having difficulty, knows the affliction as a reveal of purity and human faith degree.

AL-HAJJ (THE PILGRIMAGE)(11) « وَ مِنَ النَّاسِ مَنْ يَعْبُدُ اللَّهَ عَلَىٰ حَرْفٍ فَإِنْ أَصَابَهُ خَيْرٌ اطْمَأَنَّ بِهِ وَ إِنْ أَصَابَتْهُ فِتْنَةٌ انْقَلَبَ عَلَىٰ وَجْهِهِ » (there are among men some who serve Allah, as it were, on the verge: if good befalls them, they are, therewith, well content; but if a trial comes to them, they turn on their faces: they lose both this world and the hereafter: that is loss for all to see!)

This verse indicates that some hearts are relaxed of charity and are happy of God worship and his believe, but at the suffering and testing time, in intrigue and examination they get confused and every time they try to resort to one direction [9]. So that the verbal faith is not enough for human growth and perfection, but the hardship and persecution time is the border between the faith and dissension and determines human beings faith amount. Unlike the persuaded egos that don’t know themselves the owner of no good and evil and no benefit and harm and they see the world as a virtual life and also they know the welfare and wanting as “divine examination”, thus, the tolerance of blessing deterioration and disaster strikes will get easy for him [10]. The Qur’an put the heaven entry key as the honor of divine examination:

AL-E-IMRAN (THE FAMILY OF 'IMRAN)(142) « أَمْ حَسِبْتُمْ أَنْ تُدْخَلُوا الْجَنَّةَ وَ لَمَّا يَعْلَمِ اللَّهُ الَّذِينَ جَاهَدُوا مِنْكُمْ وَ يَعْلَمِ الصَّابِرِينَ » (did ye think that ye would enter heaven without Allah testing those of you who fought hard (in his cause) and remained steadfast?)

This imagination[login to heaven without examination] necessity is that the Muslims believe that because they are legitimate, they should never be defeated and the success and conquest are always their right. As a result, in the world they should be lucky with conquest and trophy, and in the Hereafter, they are associated with forgiveness and Heaven. while this is contrary to the guidance of divine believe[11] since in this case there is no difference between outward faith and the reality of faith and there is no concession among faith ranks.

3.2 evolution [perfect movement]

Evolution is “ the gradually movement of an object from defect to the ideal growth point” [12]. All creations are moving and becoming toward the Lord in an evolution and non-arbitrary path which is the existence honor, this becoming has been explained in four stages for every possible existence to achieve the appropriate perfection since the beginning of the universe: creation, liquidation, measurement, guidance [13]. Also human follows-up this divine mandate [14]. And in this evolution path he needs Something which purify his soul to attain the spirituality height

from the materiality and sensuality dungeon[15]. human first step in this field, is to believe. This step is the next steps start and is the soul of all of his completion steps [16].because the most valuable evolution, is human spiritual and soul perfection. That means that human reaches a strong and valuable morale for his idol because of the orientation of origin and the God love and surrender and satisfaction so that reaches the existence fact better than the best the strongest thinkers in the world [17]. One way to achieve perfection, is to step into the path of affliction and divine testing and pride. The difficulties and hardships testing, to consolidate and excitate human existence by the trainer and existence breeder. This human doesn't get experienced and pure unless he sees fall and consistencies. Human beings worldly perfection seeking in the behavior and actions which are a start for receiving the Hereafter rewards and its fruits, is emanated of factors which are associated with divine affliction.

3.2.1 Human perfection factors

The purpose of the universe creation and as a result the possibilities existence, is nothing but God knowledge and cognition. This knowledge is one of the most honorable ones, itself is inherently the aim and is the same as real luck [18] and is the most obvious of axiom [19]. Here, there is another story for human; since all the things that are in the earth are created for him [20]. He has been adorned with two blessings, wisdom and authority. his true perfection, is "Lord esteem" to realize that with God he has everything and without God nothing. This truth or "god esteem" is the existence degree in which the person inherent talent is actualized with his voluntary movement and excursion. This perfection movement, i.e., move toward divine esteem, is an inner path which begins from human heart and soul depth[21]. Since every human is evaluated toward this destination, possess strength and weakness degrees; because this is a general recognition. Although many people may not realize that or even deny that [22]. Generally, this truth cognition path is drawn of human perfection factors which are three species. Rapidly and blitz; like what has happened to some of the prophets- PBUH- such as Jesus Christ speech at birth. the moderate or slow perfection path in which believers are and the third movement, falling or descending movement or retrogressive path which is related to disbelievers and the hypocrites. The thing which causes descending and slow movement and prevents the true knowledge of the truth and God, is not ignorance, it is "negligence" [23]. Several factors are effective in this negligence creation: such as being busy with the inferior and worthless affairs in the world. What is causing this negligence elimination, is mention or heart clarifying. This mention and attention the more stronger and more focused, the more effective in pushing him toward perfection. This mention is actually "thinking" results and its strength and perfection, based on the thinking strength and perfection, varies that causes different results for different human groups [24]. Although in different perfection degree and God cognition path, attaining the highest level of that is not possible for everyone, reaching the lowest level is feasible for everyone which is believing and stepping in God slavery path and ignoring the demands and putting the force In divine satisfaction path [25]. The divine book(Qur'an) has determined some ways for understanding this cognition that one of them is taking lessons of past people destination and wise people productivity of denied users stories. Taking lessons is one of the wisdom tools to know the truth, which leads to attending, guidance and God path traversing. The people can take the path who know all the blessings and catastrophe as tools from God to be examined, be grateful for blessings and be patient for catastrophe. Devotion is another tool.

"Devotion" is to express humility, modesty, cringe extremity, obeisance and simpleness [27]. Worship is a combination for God approach and real human perfection, in Islam view point each good and beneficial affair is a worship only if its motivation is divine and pure, because all the spiritual, moral, social result root of worship is to remember God and forgot everything other [28]. Such worship, is useful for human mention and remove the negligence causes and close him to devotion degree. Whenever devotion is fixed in slave heart and soul, as he looks at everything he sees God adherence and realizes that everything that the glorified God has gifted to him is because of his grace and everything that God has inhibited is because of wisdom and this is the way that God has opened it

himself and guidance his slaves to that [29] to be a way that he will have a tool of growth, sublimation and provision to gain his goal.

This devotion itself has some tools such as: ignorance to the world. Being engaged in worldly affairs, is the main reason for forgetting and neglecting oneself [30]. Loving the world, causes to hate other things, but if human sees lots of difficulties, pains and afflictions from this world and if he is surrounded by persecutions and tribulations his interest gets lower [31]. If worldliness, is strengthen, takes place in heart and there is no space for loving God. Thus, the sign of loving God is to be away from the world [32]. Material pleasures don't attract perfect people, but they know it as their progress and perfection barrier and they just take advantage to the extent of necessity and benefit of them as a legal duty. However God favor and grace is more to someone, he avoids him of this world and its trappings more and more and makes him to understand the afflictions and temptations to arrest his attention to the Hereafter and make him to hate this world [33].

Also Subsequent deeds are the other tools. The people's life efforts will be human efforts only if they are done to achieve real perfection. The subsequent deed condition is that the God is the goal not anything else [34]. And this meaning is received by no one but the person who loves God. Such a person should remove his passions and effort in God path so that he is deserving [35]. The other tool is humility, fear and supplication toward God. Fear is "a dread with bow" [36] and a kind of heart impression which is known as a effect source and human catch it as his sanctum [37], humility is "a sincere affair toward one's glory who has humbleness". the humility position is in human heart [38]. Supplication, is to be informed of oneself defection, frustration and distraction and leads to being away from arrogant and presumptuous to a sin which brings barbarity [39]. The Qur'an says in its message:

AL-ARAF (THE HEIGHTS)(94-95) « وَ مَا أَرْسَلْنَا فِي قَرْيَةٍ مِّن نَّبِيٍّ إِلَّا أَخَذْنَا أَهْلَهَا بِالْبِأْسَاءِ وَ الضَّرَّاءِ لَعَلَّهُمْ يَضُرُّوْنَ. ثُمَّ بَدَّلْنَا مَكَانَ السَّيِّئَةِ « (whenever we sent a prophet to a town, we took up its people in suffering and adversity, in order that they might learn humility.) then we changed their suffering into prosperity, until they grew and multiplied, and began to say: "our fathers (too) were touched by suffering and affluence" ... behold! we called them to account of a sudden, while they realized not their peril)

Paying attention to Monotheism fact has been in human soul since the beginning of the creation, but due to bad parenting or blessing intoxication, he has forgotten it, but in plight and problem times, the human mentions it and remembers it again. So mention is humility introduction and the humility is supplication introduction [40]. And affliction cause this supplication, namely, the heart gets obedient toward the greatness of God and after that supplicate and moan to God port. This is the human nature that in disaster and difficulty time will grasp everything, to find a safe way for himself and since the special servants don't have a safe mean but God, become aware of him. Also the Grace God loves them too much so God himself provides a mean for discontinuity of other [41] to make them realize that they are despicable and return to God with inability and be safe from barbarity. One of the reason of affliction intensity in special servants is that they remember God in difficulties and get intimate with his mention with prayer and supplication:

AL-ANAAM (CATTLE) (42-43) « وَ لَقَدْ أَرْسَلْنَا إِلَىٰ أُمَمٍ مِّن قَبْلِكَ فَأَخَذْنَاهُمْ بِالْبِأْسَاءِ وَ الضَّرَّاءِ لَعَلَّهُمْ يَتَضَرَّوْنَ. فَلَوْ لَا إِذْ جَاءَهُمْ بَأْسُنَا تَضَرَّوْا « (before thee we sent (messengers) to many nations, and we afflicted the nations with suffering and adversity, that they might learn humility. when the suffering reached them from us, why then did they not learn humility? on the contrary their hearts became hardened, and Satan made their (sinful) acts seem alluring to them.)

Supplication to God, causes human growth and esteem and its relinquish is a sign for cruel and fascination and this way helps human to achieve a perfect human degree. Another means is patience and forbearance and "patience" verbally means "to self-control and self-preservation" in the things that wisdom and Sharia demand and it is so-called avoid of despondency and panic in the human damages [42]. The patients are the people whose thinking and view extent and spirit gentleness, have made them patient and stable and the passions whip has made them more vigilant and more conscious. unlike those who don't have a better divine purpose, in the difficulty time are disabled and they

will disappeared in this situations [43]. patience and forbearance keep human away from being impatient. Will flourish what is in human divine nature and modify what is in his material nature; since the human nature is such that in suffering is impatient and scared.

AL-MAARIJ (THE ASCENDING STAIRWAYS)(20) «إِذَا مَسَّهُ الشَّرُّ جَزُوعًا» ((fretful when evil touches him)

The patient deserves himself God grace by his patience and in perfection path, brings himself to the culmination and deserves receiving these blessings of self- confidence and lack of anxiety in dealing with tribulations and divine tests. A patient person is patient in front of blessing as he is patient against hardship and doesn't put it as his rebellion and that is when the patience, control human material aspect and his monopolization and strengthen his divine aspect, namely satisfaction, submission, patience and Spirit[44]. The Qur'an explains the patients in affliction as following:

AL-BAQARA (THE COW) (157-158) «وَلَنَبْلُوَنَّكُمْ بِشَيْءٍ مِّنَ الْخَوْفِ وَالْجُوعِ وَنَقْصٍ مِّنَ الْأَمْوَالِ وَالْأَنْفُسِ وَالتَّمَرَاتِ وَ نَبِّئِرِ الصَّابِرِينَ . أُولَئِكَ عَلَيْهِمْ صَلَوَاتٌ مِّن رَّبِّهِمْ وَ رَحْمَةٌ وَأُولَئِكَ هُمُ الْمُهْتَدُونَ»

they are those on whom (descend) blessings from allah, and mercy, and they are the ones that receive guidance. behold! safa and marwa are among the symbols of allah. so if those who visit the house in the season or at other times, should compass them round, it is no sin in them. and if any one obeyeth his own impulse to good, - be sure that Allah is he who recogniseth and knoweth.)

The best kind of the patience is that human has the knowledge of the true meaning of that and believes that and by this fact recognition, patience growth and removes any despondency and sorrow root and clarify ignorance and the appearance and credit ownership will be canceled and because the person knows that he will return to God, is not affected by the suffering and the loss of the possessions and will be the Lord's word expression:

AL-HADID (THE IRON)(22-23):

«مَا أَصَابَ مِنْ مُصِيبَةٍ فِي الْأَرْضِ وَلَا فِي أَنْفُسِكُمْ إِلَّا فِي كِتَابٍ مِّن قَبْلٍ أَنْ نَبْرَأَهَا إِنَّ ذَلِكَ عَلَى اللَّهِ يَسِيرٌ . لِكَيْلَا تَأْسَوْا عَلَىٰ مَا فَاتَكُمْ وَلَا تَفْرَحُوا بِمَا ءَاتَتْكُمْ

(no misfortune can happen on earth or in your souls but is recorded in a decree before we bring it into existence: that is truly easy for allah. in order that ye may not despair over matters that pass you by, nor exult over favours bestowed upon you. for Allah loveth not any vainglorious boaste)

All the speech is that the servant should go through these slavery path continuous stages well, to be stable when he will be in a way full of affliction and examination and difficulties, and since he has selected this way with vision seen and indeed seen, so that he will be satisfied of the divine judicial. This is the same servant who is not somber and gloomy of his lost and also is not captivated and fascinated, and this is the same evolved man whose raining is the purpose of the creation.

3.3 receiving the heavenly fruits

The perfect servant who exploits his evolution profits and fruits in the world, also in the Hereafter will not be deprived of these benefits and the most important heavenly benefits of evolution are: the preparation for meeting God.

“Liqā” verbally means “ facing with a thing” [45] and it means visibility and visual. Among the spiritual benefits for pure and perfect servants, is the promise that God has given in heralded Ascension Hadith:

“ when their soul is separating from their body, I do not send the angel of death(Zrayyl), but I will be assumed to catch their soul and I will open all the sky door for their soul and all the veils and curtains between me and them will be removed.” [47]. Reward and divine Radwan gaining is also one of the other effects. The “ satisfaction” degree, is the highest positions [48].and this position is one of the devotion status. When the prophet –PBUM- asked Gabreil about

- 24 - Khomeini, Ruhollah, Forty Hadith [Arbaein Hadith], p.323.
- 25 - Mesbah Yazdi, Mohammad Taghi, self-biology to self-altering,
- 26 - AL-E-IMRAN (THE FAMILY OF 'IMRAN)(137), «فَدَخَلْنَا مَنَقِلًا كُنَّا نَسْتَفْسِرُ وَأَيْدِيَنَا ضَيْقًا نَظُرُ وَأَكْفُنَا غِصَابًا مُمَكِّدِينَ»، many were the ways of life that have passed away before you: travel through the earth, and see what was the end of those who rejected truth.
- 27 - Raghieb Isfahani, Husseinn ibn Mohammad, Al-mofradat fi Gharib al-Qur'an, p 542.
- 28 - Motahhari, Morteza., spiritual freedom, p 185.
- 29 - ASH-SHAMS (THE SUN)(8): «فَالهِمَّاجُورُ هَاوَتْقُوبِهَا»، and its enlightenment as to its wrong and its right
- 30 - Tabatabai, Seyyed Mohammad Hossein Irfan way, p 111.
- 31 - Khomeini, Ruhollah, Forty Hadiths [Arbaeen hadith], page 240.
- 32 - Mulla Sadra, Sadr al-Din Mohammad, kasr al-asnam al-jaheliyah, p 100.
- 33 - AL-KAHF (THE CAVE)(7) «أَجْعَلْنَا مَا عَلَّمْنَا الْأَنْبِيَاءَ مِنْ بَيْنَتِهِمْ لِنَبْلُوهُمُ أَيُّهُمْ أَحْسَنُ عَمَلًا»، that which is on earth we have made but as a glittering show for the earth, in order that we may test them - as to which of them are best in conduct.
- (Khomeini, Ruhollah, Forty Hadiths [Arbaeen hadith], page 240.
- 34 – An-Nisa(the women)(122), «الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا وَعَمِلُوا الصَّالِحَاتِ»، but those who believe and do deeds of righteousness, - we shall soon admit them to gardens, with rivers flowing beneath, -to dwell therein for ever. allah's promise is the truth, and whose word can be truer than allah's?
- 35 - Mulla Sadra, Sadr al-Din Mohammad, Kasr al-asnam al-jaheliyah, p 139.
- 36 - Raghieb Isfahani, Husseinn ibn Mohammad, Al-mofradat fi Gharib al-Qur'an, p 283.
- 37 - Javadi Amoli, Abdullah, the Prophet PBUT - life(sire)in Quran, vol 2, p 87.
- 38 - Bent Al-shaty, Aisha Abdul Rahman, the verbal magic of Qur'an), p 240.
- 39 - Modaresi, Mohammad Taghi, man hoda al-Quran(who guide Qur'an, vol 3, p 336.
- 40 - Makarem Shirazi, Nasser, al-amsal fi tafsir al-ketab Allah al-manzel, vol 3, p 336.
- 41 - Khomeini, Ruhollah, Forty Hadiths [Arbaeen hadith], page 241.
- 42 - Javadi Amoli, Abdullah, the Prophet life - PBUT in Quran, vol 2, p 79.
- 43 - Taleghani, Mahmoud, the light of Qur'an, vol 2, p 2.
- 44 - Javadi Amoli, Abdullah, the Prophet life - PBUT in Quran, vol 2, p 78.
- 45 - Raghieb Isfahani, Husseinn ibn Mohammad, Al-mofradat fi Gharib al-Qur'an, p 745.
- 46 - Khomeini, Ruhollah, Forty Hadiths [Arbaeen hadith], page 452.
- 47 -Majlesi, Mohammad Baghir, Bihar alanvar al-jamea ledarar akhbar al-aemat al-athar, vol 74, p 24.
- 48 - Tayyib, AbdulHossein, Atyb al-bayan fi tafsir al-Qur'an vol 8, p 456.
- 49 - Majlesi, Mohammad Baghir Bihar alanvar al-jamea ledarar akhbar al-aemat al-athar, vol 20, p 74.

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